

ROLE OF NUMBERS IN HUMAN WORTH AND DEVELOPMENT

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Humanism is a concept that expresses concern for human dignity, freedom, happiness, equal rights, creation of conditions for the manifestation of all the principles of humanity. According to him, the most valuable thing in the world is a human being, the whole being should serve the human being and his happiness. Caring for human destiny, national interests, people of the country is the main issue of humanitarianism.

Humanitarian ideas have a long history. They have been reflected in folklore, literature, religious and philosophical teachings in the form of dreams of happiness and justice.

In our republic, step by step, from year to year the material and spiritual well-being of our people is increasing, education of the mature generation is improving. In other words, the "Year of the Perfect Generation" is continuing as a logical continuation of the previous years.

The role of science in raising a perfect generation is incomparable, and we encounter numbers and numbers in acquiring many specialties.

In the development of human society, in general, the role of numbers and numbers in raising the scientific potential of humanity is incomparable. There is no area where numbers and figures have not penetrated. Numbers and figures are everywhere now. Any object, place - area, thing or event has its scale expressed in numbers. That is why numbers and figures have generalization, separation and differentiation signs and properties. This situation can be clearly seen in the laws of dialectics in philosophy in a shorter sense, including the law of transition of

quantitative changes to qualitative changes. Changes in number and quantity necessarily lead to changes in quality. When we look for meaning in any number and number, we first relate to it. We can say that this situation gives rise to the philosophy of numbers in a certain sense.

Today, we face debates on philosophy of life, philosophy of nature, philosophy of man, philosophy of history, philosophy of society and other such topics. Based on this logic, we gathered some of our opinions about the role of numbers and numbers in general life, human life, and the development of society, and decided to call it the philosophy of numbers in a certain sense. In the words of Abu Nasr Farabi, "if knowledge about existence is acquired, if education is given about it, if the nature of things from existence is known, if the meaning of things is understood, if various beliefs and ideas about this thing appear in the mind based on reliable documents, then we call the science of this information philosophy". We believe that these ideas also apply to the philosophy of numbers.

From the earliest times of human society, many tribes communicated with each other using different numbers and numerals. During the period of the primitive community, numbers served as a kind of independent language. The letters of some ancient alphabets, including the ancient Jewish alphabet, were given quantitative meaning. In ancient times, people sought to know the future by interpreting the meaning of numbers. In this way, numerology, which deals with numbers and figures, was gradually formed as a science. According to the sources that have reached us, numerologists were in Rome, Babylon, Egypt, India, Greece and other countries. In those times, mathematics and philosophy were used to determine various calculations and phenomena.

In fact, these two disciplines have complemented and supported each other. Al-Kindi, a scholar of the East, assigns a special place to mathematics in the study of philosophical sciences. According to him, philosophy as a science is the science of number and harmony (proportion), which is based on mathematics, which studies the science of geometry and stars.

Philosophical laws, categories are not expressed in the language of mathematics, but mathematical laws, concepts are analyzed philosophically, because particularity is only a form of generality. Determining the relationship between the same forms of law is also a philosophical issue.

Pythagoras is a famous Greek philosopher and mathematician who studied numerology and founded it. He invented the relationship between the musical intervals of his time and the numbers 1 to 4. Pythagoras did not stop at his results, but a certain combination of numbers determined the sacred number. This combination reflects the perfection of the Earth, its material and metaphysical unity. Pythagoras' discovery of the relationship between numbers and notes led to his new invention, namely, the discovery that all events on Earth are connected with numbers.

The basics of numerology dealing with numbers were reflected in the activities of various European secret societies - Freemasons, Anthroposophists, Rosicrucians and other societies, but thanks to them, numerology was slowly formed, continuing to reveal new secrets for humanity, and has reached us.

Of particular importance was their doctrine of even and odd numbers in relation to various geometric shapes. A point is one number, two is a straight line, three is a plane, and four is a body. The universe and the things in it were created from number.

According to the Pythagorean theory, number 1 is the basis of everything and events in the world, number 2 is the basis of opposites in nature, number 3 is the unity of opposites, that is, the unity of opposite sides of objects, number 4 is the form of four elements.

The teachings of Kabbalah also dealt with the interpretation of numbers. A unique type of numerology is called Gematria. The Pythagorean concept was much expanded. Kabbalists made magic squares out of numbers. After the discovery of the nature of electricity, light and magnetism in the 19th century, numerologists began to give numerical meaning to energy vibrations.

Since ancient times, people have been interested in the meaning of numbers and numbers, that is, in a certain sense, the philosophy of numbers.

In numerology, the most important number for a person is his date of birth. This number affects a person's life and character.

Under which moon number a person was born depends on his emotions and spiritual condition. The number of the year of birth affects the way of thinking of a person and reflects his interest in this or that activity.

Jean-Jacques Rousseau said that "before making a person a philosopher, it is necessary to educate him as a human being." Even if the processes on earth seem to be chaotic, in fact, as the Nobel laureate I. Prigozhin specifically emphasized, they take place on the basis of mutual cooperation and self-organization. Recognizing their existence on the basis of their causal connection, which is a specific system, he called it synergetics. Accordingly, we think that a person's name, day, month, and year of birth help him to know who he is, to understand himself (Socrates), to be able to control himself, and to find his place in life in general.

Currently, some leaders abroad are interested in the numerological cards of their subordinates. This work can be started in our country, of course.

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